

Research Article

Biodegradable Self-Regulating Fertiliser Beads

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Abstract: Chemical fertilisers use pose significant environmental risks, primarily the soil and water. The development of a biodegradable, self-regulating fertiliser from domestic waste is essential for boosting crop productivity while mitigating the excessive nutrient release problems commonly associated with chemical fertilisers. This study developed a biodegradable slow-release fertiliser and its vessels to promote an environmentally friendly solution which supports the United Nations' SDGs 12, 14, and 15. Calcium carbonate, nitrogen, and potassium were extracted from eggshells, tea grounds, and banana peels, respectively, and bound with aloe vera gel and cornstarch for slow nutrient release. The formed beads withstood an average of 755 g load pressure. In a 3-day trial, onion plants treated with the biofertiliser showed 47.8% leaf growth and one new leaf, outperforming chemical fertilisers (22.2%, no new leaf). At Technology Readiness Level 6, further studies will assess soil decomposition and effects on root development.

Keywords: slow nutrient release; fertiliser; crop; biodegradable; sustainability.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fertiliser use is a common practice in agriculture to boost crop productivity. However, the conventional chemical fertilisers pose an undesirable impact to the environment due to its rapid nutrient release action that pollutes the water and soil. Excessive use of chemical fertilisers has caused increased soil salinity, buildup of heavy metals, eutrophication, and excessive nitrate accumulation which threatens environmental and agricultural sustainability (Savci, 2012).

A more controlled fertiliser release is preferred as means to supply the crops with the desired amount, for a longer period. This can be achieved through the use of slow-release fertiliser vessels which are made up of coatings and chemical inhibitors that modulates the fertiliser release to soil (E. et al., 2024). This solution minimised excessive fertiliser nutrient accumulation in soil, mitigating soil

pollution and water pollution, should the fertiliser leach into the water system. The vessel and fertiliser can be made even more environmentally friendly by utilising naturally occurring materials from soil, plants and animals, which these materials can naturally degrade. Biodegradable fertilisers typically have lower toxicity compared to synthetic alternatives, making them safer for plants, animals, and humans (Alvarenga et al., 2007). This makes them more efficient and less damaging to the environment

This study proposes an eco-friendly solution: biodegradable fertiliser beads made from eggshells, banana peels, and coffee grounds, which supply calcium, potassium, and nitrogen (Kopeć et al., 2024). These nutrients are embedded in a biodegradable hydrogel made from aloe vera leaf gel, acting as a controlled-release matrix to match plant uptake. The project aims to reduce dependence on synthetic fertilisers by utilizing natural waste, offering a sustainable and efficient alternative, meeting the sustainable development goals (SDGs): SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production), 14 (life below water) and 15 (Life on land).

2. METHOD AND MATERIAL

2.1 Preparation bead fertiliser

The bead fertiliser vessel was prepared following the outlined method by Ahmed (2015) with modifications. 50 g Aloe vera extract initially heated and then 10 g cornstarch was added as a gel thickening agent. The fertiliser ingredients used were 15 g eggshells to supplement calcium carbonate, 15 g banana peels for potassium, and 15 g coffee beans for nitrogen. The fertiliser ingredients were baked for 30 minutes at 250° C in a conventional oven to extract the nutrients and remove moisture. The ingredients that were baked were then ground in a blender and followed by mortar and pestle into fine powder. The fine powder was added into the hydrogel base and mixed thoroughly. The mixture was then shaped into spherical shape and finally dried on a white tile for 24 hours at room temperature until it is hardened (Figure 1). The video of the product is available and can be accessed online via <https://youtu.be/N1aJaq92m0>.

Figure 1. Biodegradable Self-regulating Fertiliser Beads

2.2 Number of leaves and leaf growth evaluation

The bead fertiliser beads were tested on 3-week-old potted onion plants for 3 days. We monitored the growth of the plant by the number of leaves and change in leaf height. All onion plants were initially measured at 15.0 cm height. The onion plants with no fertiliser added were labelled as A1 and A2, with the hydrogel beads were labelled B1 and B2 while the onion plants with chemical fertilisers were labelled C1 and C2.

2.3 Fertiliser bead strength test

The strength test measured the mass each sample could support to assess the bead’s resilience against mechanical stress. The strength test was conducted by placing increasing weights on the hydrogel fertiliser beads until they broke or deformed. Four different bead samples were tested, labelled as Test 1, Test 2, Test 3, and Test 4. The maximum weight each bead could support was recorded. Test 1 and Test 4 showed the highest strength, holding 910 g and 900 g respectively, while Test 2 and Test 3 supported only 610 g and 600 g.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Number of Leaves

There were no significant differences among the onion plants A, B and C (Table 1). There was one leaf increment observed for A2, B2 and C2, but no leaf increase observed for A1, B1 and C1. This indicates a no significant difference impact of the bead fertiliser and chemical fertiliser to the amount of leaves within the 3-day experimental period.

Table 1. Onion plant number of leaves using different fertiliser treatments.

Onion plant	Number of leaves	
	Initial	Final
A1	7	7
A2	11	12
B1	15	16
B2	7	8
C1	9	9
C2	4	5

3.2 Leaves growth

The onion leaves from the control group showed a diverse growth pattern ranging from 1.5 cm (A1) to 6.9 cm (A2) (Table 2). The bead fertiliser onion plant, B1 and B2 showed a greater leaves’ growth than the chemical fertiliser group, C1 and C2. This suggested a greater growth promoting effect of our bead fertiliser compared to the conventional chemical fertiliser.

Table 2. Onion plant leaves growth under different fertiliser treatments.

Onion plant	Leaves growth (cm)
A1	1.5
A2	6.9
B1	4.8
B2	4.9
C1	3.1
C2	3.6

3.3 Fertiliser bead strength test

Test 1 and Test 4 showed the highest strength, with bearing load of masses 910 g and 900 g respectively (Table 3). In contrast, Test 2 and Test 3 had lower strength, supporting only 610 g and 600 g. This yielded an average load bearing of 755 g.

Table 3. Onion plant strength test

Experiment	Mass (g)
Test 1	910
Test 2	610
Test 3	600
Test 4	900
Average	755

4. DISCUSSION

The data from the experiment shows that the organic fertiliser had a significant positive impact on plant growth in terms of increased leaf height. The bead fertiliser demonstrated a greater leaves growth than the chemical fertiliser group. This growth can be attributed to the fertiliser's rich nutrient content, including nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, which promote cell elongation and vigorous growth. The slow-release nature of the fertiliser provides a steady supply of nutrients, ensuring optimal plant development without the risk of over-fertilization.

Furthermore, the bead fertiliser's better growth performance compared to the chemical fertiliser supplemented onion plants may also suggests the potential inhibitive effects of excessive nutrient accumulation in soil from chemical fertiliser application that hinder optimal plant growth (Savci, 2012). Additionally, the organic matter in the fertiliser improves soil structure, enhancing moisture retention and supporting beneficial soil microorganisms, which may also explain the better growth performance of the bead fertiliser-applied onion plants (E. et al., 2024). This combination of improved soil quality and balanced nutrient availability results in enhanced growth, with taller plants as observed in the experiment. In summary, the organic fertiliser supports sustained plant growth. However, the time constraint of this study limits our findings to only 3 days. At a longer observation period, we could potentially observe a more significant growth performance difference between our bead fertiliser compared to chemical fertilisers and no fertiliser treatment groups.

5. CONCLUSION

The development of biodegradable self-regulating fertiliser beads demonstrates strong potential as a sustainable alternative to synthetic fertilisers. Our evaluation of plant's growth and strength suggested the beads effectively support early plant growth, provide sufficient nutrients, and maintain structural integrity under moderate pressure. The absence of leaf discoloration and the measurable increase in plant height and leaf number within a short period highlight their effectiveness. This fertiliser bead is at Technology Readiness Level 6. Future studies will focus on field trials and decomposition analysis to further evaluate their environmental impact, nutrient release profile, and long-term agronomic viability.

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